

Standard Operating Procedures for Acquisition of Digital Health Ecological Momentary Assessment and Passive sensing Accelerating Medicines Partnership® SCHIZOPHRENIA

An observational study examining clinical trajectories and predictors of outcomes in the clinical high risk population.

Version 2.5, 11 DEC 2023

Procedure	Visit 1	Visit 2	Visit 3	Visit 4	Visit 5	Visit 6	Visit 7	Visit 8	Visit 9	Visit 10	Visit 11	Visit 12	Visit 13	Visit 14	Visit 15	Visit 16	Conversion
Month	-3 to -1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	18	24	-
Consent Form																	
Interview/ Questionnaire																	
Cognitive Tasks																	
MRI*																	
EEG*																	
Blood and Saliva Samples*																	
Actigraphy (daily)																	
Digital Data (daily passive sensing, EMA, audio diary)																	
Free Speech Sampling (audio and facial recording)																	
PSYCHS (audio recording)																	

* In-person visit

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Version Modification Log

Version	Date	Summary of Changes
1.1	7 June 2021	- First integrated set-up of SOP
1.2	27 Aug 2021	- Response scale of EMA items changed from 0-100 to 1-7 - Formatting of text and screenshots - Screenshot of scattered data and feedback in app added - Detailed instruction on how to complete the diaries added - Financial compensation schedule changed to 3-monthly - Decision moment (go/no go) after two months added - Checking in with participant extended
1.3	22 Oct 2021	- Actigraphy to separate SOP - Instructions formatted into table - EMA items moved to appendix - Training schedule added
1.4	6 Nov 2021	- Updates after testing, practical improvements
1.5	22 Dec 2021	- Updates after testing, practical improvements - Added expected number of participants
1.6	21 Jan 2022	- Added face page - Added version modification log - Added mindLAMP overview section - Separated orientation section into smaller subsections - Added more screenshots to mindLAMP installation section - Updated screenshots in “3.3 Explain the App” - Updated screenshots in “4.1 Before checking in with the participant” - Added explanation of each EMA item - Ensured consistent formatting for headings and tables
1.7	26 Jan 2022	- Updated version modification log
1.8	4 Feb 2022	- Removed go/no go decision after 2 months; focus on monthly check-in (premature ending can now only be participant-initiated) - Added different payment schedule for PRESCIENT - Changed time window for responding mindLAMP from 90 min to 5 hours - Added that survey can be assessed through “Assess” tab if 5-hour time window is exceeded - Changed wording in explanation use of GPS data - Added emphasis on completing surveys around the same time every day - Changed order of EMA items in overview of items and Appendix
1.9	11 Feb 2022	- Swapped DropBox mindLAMP tutorial links for open-access public YouTube Video Links (pp. 33-34) - Added/Edited 6a. and 6b. in installing mindLAMP section (pp. 11-12), which provides guidance on how to review and select appropriate sensors according to a participant’s choice
2.0	04 Mar 2022	- Edited Overview to include explanation of each sensor type - Amended participant login credentials and added AMP SCZ ID as alias - Added network-specific password instructions - Removed ‘Health’ app and ‘Google Fit’ requirement - Added links to mindLAMP user guide and forum for reporting bugs and issues, and mindLAMP contact details to the Appendix - Updated reimbursement schedule for PRESCIENT

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moved reimbursement schedule from Appendix to Orientation session - Highlighted possibility of battery drainage due to GPS sensor - Added voice diary instructions - Added instructions for participants to view their own data - Summarised permissions settings into table format - Summarised reimbursement schedule into table format
2.1	08 Mar 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Included permission settings monthly check - Added email script to participants
2.2	24 Mar 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changed survey completion window from 5 to 6 hours - Removed QR code and one-time login instructions from email script
2.3	15 Apr 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Added in ProNET reimbursement information in financial reimbursement schedule
2.4	19 Apr 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Edited PRESCIENT reimbursement information for participants who withdraw from study - Added different study versions - Edit Q22 from 'I felt like undertaking something' to 'I felt motivated'
2.5	21 Apr 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ProNET server domain added
2.6	5 May 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description of study versions included - Reimbursement information updated
2.7	30 May 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changed battery saver / low power mode requirement (Study Ver. 1 only) - Updated Email Script - Amended monitoring progress protocol - Added protocol to guide participants to enter 'dummy data' at orientation session - Minor updates to wording - Updated contact persons for PRESCIENT and ProNET - Moved Portal walkthrough to Section 3.4. and updated wording
2.8	28 Apr 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minor updates to wording - Updated ProNET server domain - Updated outdated hyperlinks - Updated reimbursement schedule for PRESCIENT - Updated Android minimum system requirement - Updated data confidentiality script - Updated app permission setting guide - Added link to Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) - Added notes on RPMS and REDCap forms to Overview - Added additional notes to voice recording and passive sensing data explanation - Added elaboration of mobile data and WiFi usage - Added description about disabling low power mode as a prerequisite for optimal GPS sensor functioning - Added complex password instructions for ProNET - Added mindLAMP Bug Report Form - Added instructions for participant study withdrawal
2.9	13 Jul 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updated Quality Control section for Passive Sensor Data
3.0	8 Aug 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Section 2.3: Updated Email Script (reimbursement schedule & permissions) - Section 3.5: Updated reimbursement schedule for PRESCIENT - Section 4: Updated monitoring progress with DPDash and DPACC QC Report instructions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Added DPDash overview o Added 1-week post-baseline check-in instructions o Updated pre-monthly check-in instructions

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Updated monthly check-in instructions - Section 5: Added ad hoc correspondence & procedures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Instructions for participant changing survey version ○ Procedure for non-participant triggered missingness - Section 6: Updated premature end procedure - Updated battery saver / low power mode requirement (Study Ver. 1 and 2) - Updated SOP Title as per FDA and NIMH's guidance - Edited Overview section to be consistent with current update - Minor updates to wording - Added DPDash guide to Appendix
3.1	11 Dec 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updated PRESCIENT contact persons - Updated ProNET reimbursement schedule
		-

Overview

mindLAMP

- mindLAMP will be used to measure Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) and collect Passive Sensing data.
- Data will be collected via the mindLAMP 2 app, which can be installed on Apple and Android smartphones.

Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA)

- EMA will repeatedly measure participants' symptoms and behaviour over a course of 12 months.
- mindLAMP will prompt participants every evening at 8pm to:
 - complete a short 30-item text survey* assessing their mood, stress levels, experiences, and behaviour, and
 - make a 2-minute voice diary recording their recent experiences. This component is optional.
- Participants will receive reimbursement for completing text surveys. See [Section 3.5](#) for more details.

*See [Appendix I](#) for a full list of survey items.

Passive sensing (PS)

- Passive sensing will automatically log context information via mobile phone sensors over a course of 12 months.
- mindLAMP will capture three types of passive sensing data **:
 - GPS sensor[#] – Participants' location estimates.
 - Accelerometer sensor – Physical acceleration: whether the phone is in motion or not.
 - Device state sensor – Records screen status (on or off). It **does not** record time spent within specific apps.
- Raw data will be transformed into metrics like 'home time', 'time spent outdoors', 'sleep duration', and 'phone usage'. Personally identifiable data **will not** be stored in this study.

**[Click here](#) for more information on each sensor type. #GPS collection may result in battery drain.

Study versions

Versions	Sensors and activities included
AMP_SCZ v1: Full Study	Text survey, voice diary, accelerometer, device state, GPS
AMP_SCZ v2: Full Study Without GPS	Text survey, voice diary, accelerometer, device state
AMP_SCZ v3: Surveys Only	Text survey, voice diary

Monthly check-ins

- Study personnel will monitor & check in with participants monthly (i.e., check DPACC QC Report & DPDash)
- Where possible, one research assistant should be assigned to the same participant for the duration of the study.

RPMS (PRESCIENT) / REDCap (ProNET)

- Any protocol deviations and notes must be documented in the corresponding forms with dates.
 - Example: "20221019 - participant did not receive survey notifications."

mindLAMP Bug Report Form

- Complete the [mindLAMP Bug Report Form](#) if there are any issues with the mindLAMP app or dashboard.

^^ Copy this if the link above does not work: <https://forms.gle/UzXed2jZuPG1HnbA>

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

- Click [here](#) to view frequently asked questions.

^^ Copy this if the link above does not work: <https://nih.box.com/s/vtk0b1lq459gqlnv6j8ghd4j22k57iy1>

1. Study setup

Note: Only needs to be completed once at the beginning of the study.

1.1. Overview of mindLAMP

- The mindLAMP platform consists of two components:
 - o **Smartphone app:** To collect multi-modal data (e.g., EMA and passive sensing) from participants
 - o **Dashboard:** To configure study elements (e.g., survey timing, reminders) and monitor participants' progress

1. Log into the mindLAMP dashboard

- Visit: <https://dashboard.lamp.digital/#/>
- Select your preferred language
- Enter server domain:
 - PRESCIENT: **mindlamp.orygen.org.au**
 - ProNET: **mindlamp-api.pronet.med.yale.edu**
- Enter the email address and password specific to your site.

2. Toggle Advanced Mode

Important: You must enable Advanced Mode to 'Add a User' (i.e., study participants).

3. The mindLAMP dashboard

Note: The first time you log in, you will see the dashboard in its default "Simple Mode". Toggling to "Advanced Mode" will display all tabs on the left. This setting will be saved for future logins.

- To manage user accounts → Users
- To create study-specific tasks for participants (e.g., surveys, voice recording) → Activities
- To manage sensor data → Sensors
- To view study versions → Studies
- To inspect data quality (e.g., passive data collection rate) → Data Portal

User account
Every LAMP ID begins with "U" and is suffixed by 10 random numbers.

Multiple login credentials can be generated through each User account.

- To manage credentials
- To configure reminder notifications
- To monitor participant progress (e.g., number of surveys completed)

2. Preparation for orientation session with participants

2.1. Create a user account

- Before onboarding a new participant, create a new account for them via the mindLAMP dashboard.

<p>1. Add a new user account:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click '+ Add' - Select 'Add a user' <p>Important: <u>Never</u> select 'Add a new group' or 'Add a new user and group.'</p>	
<p>2. Save the new user account to the appropriate group:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select version participant consented to. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click 'SAVE'. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The new account will appear in the Users tab, along with a green update dialog. - Do not close the green update dialog. 	

3. Default login credentials:

- Click the **∨** (down arrow) symbol in the update dialog.

- Default login credentials format:

Email address: **LAMP_ID@lamp.com**
(e.g., U0123456789@lamp.com)

Password: **LAMP_ID**
(e.g., U0123456789)

Important:

- Emails and passwords are case sensitive.

Temporary email address
U6120168572@lamp.com

Temporary password
U6120168572

LAMP ID

One-time login link
https://dashboard.lamp.digital/#/?a=VTYxMj#

4. Add participant's AMP SCZ ID as alias:

- Click on the **✎** (pencil symbol) beside the new LAMP ID.

- Add the participant's AMP SCZ ID to the field.

- Click on the **✓** (tick symbol) to save.

5. Add clinician/research assistant's name:

- Click on the **🔑** (key button).

- Click on **T** (blue circle with "T").

- Select 'Update Photo & Role'

- Add name of research assistant who has been assigned to this participant to the field.

- Click on the ✓ (tick symbol) to save.

Important:

- Update this field if the assigned research assistant changes.

Manage Credentials

T +

+

Ann Ee Ching ✓

Save Role & Photo

Enter the family member or clinician's role here. For this credential to appear as a member, either a photo or role MUST be saved.

2.2. Set up password

PRESCIENT

- a) PRESCIENT will be using the default password set up by mindLAMP:

Successfully created Participant U6120168572 ^
 . Tap the expand icon on the right to see credentials and details. x

Temporary email address
 U6120168572@lamp.com

Temporary password
U6120168572

One-time login link
 https://dashboard.lamp.digital/#/?a=VTYxMjF

Note: If there are site-specific requirements for a different password, please follow Steps 1.a. and 1.b. on the right column.

ProNET

1. Set up a complex password as per Yale's requirement:

- a) Click on (blue circle with 'T').

- b) Select 'Reset Password'.

- c) Configure complex password as per instructions here: <https://docs.lamp.digital/deploy/passwords/>

- d) Click on the (tick symbol) to save.

2.3. Email participants their login credentials and other important information

<p>1. Email participants using the email template:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Copy and paste the participant’s login credentials. - Use email template here. See example below. <p>Important:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Copy this if the link above does not work: https://nih.box.com/s/xc5zauvtlc9vgir7hsb34noz8fd3y6t1 - For non-English sites, please translate the Email Script to your local language if you have non-English speaking participants. 	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p style="background-color: #4CAF50; color: white; padding: 2px;">Successfully created Participant U6120168572 Tap the expand icon on the right to see credentials and details.</p> <div style="border: 1px solid red; padding: 2px;"> <p>Temporary email address U6120168572@lamp.com</p> <p>Temporary password U6120168572</p> </div> <p>One-time login link https://dashboard.lamp.digital/#/?a=VTYxMjI/</p> </div>
<p>#start script#</p> <p>Yellow highlight: to be edited and/or deleted if not applicable</p> <p>Hi Participant Name,</p> <p>Thank you for taking part in this study. Please do not delete this email until you complete this part of the study (i.e., 1 year from now).</p> <p>mindLAMP login details</p> <p>Domain: mindlamp.orygen.org.au (PRESCIENT) / mindlamp-api.pronet.med.yale.edu (ProNET) Email: LAMP_ID@lamp.com (e.g, UXXXXXXXXXX@lamp.com) Password: LAMP_ID (e.g, UXXXXXXXXXX)</p> <p>Survey schedule</p> <p>You will receive a notification for the survey at 8pm every day. Please <u>complete it as soon as possible</u>, before you go to bed. You may also record any experience you might have during the day using the voice diary.</p> <p>We recommend setting an alarm for the daily surveys. Other participants have found this helpful.</p> <p>Please make sure that you have enabled the relevant permissions (location, notification, audio) on your phone to ensure data collection. Please make sure you never turn on battery saver / low power mode at any time. *</p> <p>*Please remove if the participant is enrolling into [AMP_SCZ v3: Surveys Only]</p> <p>Reimbursement</p> <p>Reimbursement is dependent on the number of surveys you complete. You will receive more reimbursement if you complete more surveys.</p>	

PRESCIENT	ProNET
Schedule: - initial 10 AUD reimbursement (Month 0) - every month since EMA baseline	Schedule: every 3 months (Month 3, 6, 9, 12)
Every month since baseline: 0.40 AUD per completed survey/audio diary Number of days completed x 0.40 = <u> </u> AUD	Every 3 months: 2 USD per completed survey/audio diary Number of days completed x 2 = <u> </u> USD
Study Contact Details	
Insert RA's work email Insert RA's work phone number	
Troubleshooting / Questions	
If you experience any technical difficulties or have any questions, please contact me by replying to this email.	
Again, thank you for taking the time to be part of this study. We really appreciate it.	
Kind regards, Researcher's Name	
#end script#	
2. Update LAMP_ID (XXXXXXXXXXXX) on: - PRESCIENT – EMA, Month 0 on RPMS - ProNET – Digital Biomarkers Mindlamp Onboarding on REDCap	

*For non-English sites, please translate the Email Script to your local language if you have non-English speaking participants.

3. Orientation session with participants (face-to-face)

3.1. Introduce the study

<p>1.1 Explain the purpose of EMA/PS research.</p>	<p><i>“In research, we often use surveys or interviews to understand how you’ve been doing over the last few weeks. This is like taking a snapshot of your life.</i></p> <p><i>Another way of exploring how you’re doing and what you’re up to is to investigate it in real time! Instead of doing just one survey, we will ask you to do a quick survey every day. This is like making a ‘movie’, rather than taking a single ‘picture’. This way, we gain insight into how your experiences unfold over time.</i></p> <p><i>The goal is to see if we can predict how someone will be feeling or doing after one year, based on the pattern of your responses.”</i></p>
<p>1.2 Explain how EMA will take place.</p>	<p><i>“To do this, we will use a phone app, called mindLAMP. You can download it for free! For one year, you will complete a survey every evening in this app. The survey includes questions about your thoughts and feelings for that day, like: ‘Today I felt relaxed’ or ‘Today I felt stressed’. It takes only 2 minutes, and you will get faster the more you do them! You can also record a voice diary about how your day went.”</i></p>
<p>1.3 Explain how passive sensing will take place.</p> <p>Note: Omit mentioning this part if participant is in AMP_SCZ v3.</p>	<p><i>“Your phone automatically collects data, like your location and movements. The mindLAMP app will capture these data and send them to a secure server, where they turn into metrics, like how much time you spend at home each day or how long you sleep every night. Aside from enabling some permissions on your phone, there is nothing else you need to do for this data to be collected. This data may inform how different environments and activities impact your health.”</i></p> <p>AMP_SCZ v1: Full Study only:</p> <p><i>“The recruitment team will not be able to access or see where you are. Do note that the location/GPS sensor may result in phone battery drain.”</i></p>
<p>1.4 Emphasize importance of EMA and passive sensing studies.</p>	<p><i>“We understand that this is quite a lot to ask, completing a survey every day for a year. This is a new way of doing research and the information you provide is incredibly valuable. It will be much more detailed than answering a questionnaire just once. By making sense of your experiences over time, we can better predict who needs help or is likely to do well. This can greatly improve our mental health practices.”</i></p>
<p>1.5 Emphasize the importance of good compliance.</p>	<p><i>“As you can imagine, it is really important to complete as many surveys as possible.</i></p> <p><i>Your data are like pieces in a jigsaw puzzle. If we don’t have all the pieces, then we can’t get the full picture! If we have lots of missing data, then we’ll be studying very incomplete patterns, like this figure here (show figure below). So, please do your best and complete as many surveys as you can.”</i></p>

Tip: If running the orientation online, paste the following graphs in a separate Word document to share.

1.6 Describe **benefits** to participants:

a) financial reimbursement

a) *“The more surveys you complete, the more reimbursement you will receive. I will explain more about this later when we discuss practicalities.”*

b) personalised feedback

Note: Highlight this and really motivate participants

b) *“You can also view and track your personal data in the mindLAMP app. Some of our participants have found the ability to monitor their own mood a great tool to gain insight into and regulate their emotions. Many participants found this the best part of being in the study and said that they would like to continue monitoring their responses even after the study ended. This is an example of what the data looks like:”*

c) contribution to research.

c) *“You will be contributing to state-of-the-art science and help researchers learn more about mental health in daily life. The information we gather in this study will be of great value to mental health practices and the mental health of young people.”*

2. Answer any remaining questions.

“Does this sound OK? Do you have any questions?”

3.2. Install mindLAMP

- Minimum system requirement: Android 8 or iOS 14 or higher.

<p>1. Note details of participant's phone*:</p> <p>Phone model: ____ (e.g., iPhone 11) Software version: ____ (e.g., version 14.8.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If participant's phone cannot support mindLAMP, provide a study phone. <p>*Important: Necessary for troubleshooting.</p>	
<p>2. Explain to the participant that there are multiple ways to stop data collection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>"If you no longer wish to participate, you can either remove the app from your phone or let us know."</i> 	
<p>Install on iPhone - requires minimum iOS 14</p>	
<p>3.1 Open App Store.</p> <p>3.2 Download mindLAMP 2.</p>	<p>3.1 Open Play Store.</p> <p>3.2 Download mindLAMP 2.</p>
<p>4. Enter login credentials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select participant's preferred language - Enter server domain: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ PRESCIENT: mindlamp.orygen.org.au ▪ ProNET: mindlamp-api.pronet.med.yale.edu - Enter email address and password as per Section 2.2. - Select Login <p>Note: If participants ask to change their password, follow the instructions in Section 2.2.1.a.</p>	

5. Review the sensor data collection options below. Guide participants to **enable permissions** on their phone based on the components they have opted in.

Important: Relevant permissions must be accepted. Otherwise, the chosen sensor data will not be collected.

Sensor Type	Permission Settings	
	iPhone	Android*
Text survey	Enable notification permissions	
Voice diary	Enable microphone/audio permissions	
	Go to mindLAMP > Assess > Voice Recording	
GPS	Enable location permissions	
	Go to Settings > mindLAMP 2 > Location	
Other permissions		

*These are the permission settings for a Samsung. Other Android phones might differ slightly.

6. AMP_SCZ v1: Full Study and AMP_SCZ v2: Full Study Without GPS:

Instruct the participant to **never enable Low Power Mode**. This is a prerequisite for optimal passive sensor functioning.

3.3. Demonstrate how to use mindLAMP app

- **Do not** end the orientation session until you verify that the participant can use the app **independently** and **confidently**.
- Briefly **explore the interface of the app** with the participant before elaborating on each section.

<p>1. The Daily Survey can be accessed one of three ways:</p>		
<p>Method 1: via push notifications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - notifications will be sent out at 8PM 		
<p>a) Remind participant about their response time window:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>“You will receive a notification at 8PM. Please complete the survey between 8PM and the time you go to bed. Please try to complete the surveys around the same time every day. If this is not possible, please complete it as soon as possible. Surveys will not be saved if they are partially completed.”</i> 		
<p>b) Let participants know that the mindLAMP add does not use mobile data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>“The app does not use mobile data at all. Data will only be uploaded when your mobile device is connected to WiFi.”</i> 		
<p>c) Open 'Daily Survey' and select 'Start Survey'.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>“Let’s briefly explore the app’s interface before we go through each section in detail.”</i> 		

- d) The survey will display one question at a time.
- The **progress bar** at the top will display the participant's survey completion progress.
 - Select **'Next'** or **'Back'** to navigate through the questions.

- e) On the last question, complete the survey by selecting **'Submit'**.
- A pop-up will appear to show the participant their survey streak.

2. Voice Diary can be access via the Assess tab:

- a) Open **'Voice Recording'** and select **'Begin'**.

b) To begin recording:

- Select **'Allow'** to enable microphone access.
- Click the (microphone) symbol to begin recording.

c) To upload recording:

- Click the (stop) symbol.
- Select **'Upload'** to upload recording.

Note: Participants can select 'Clear' if they wish to delete the recording and record again.

d) Two pop ups will appear if your upload is successful.

3. Participant may view their own responses via the Portal tab.

- *"You can view your responses via the Portal tab. Let's go through the survey questions now so you can have a look what your responses look like here."*

3.4. Explore each section of mindLAMP in detail with the participant

<p>1. Daily Surveys</p> <p>a) Explain that everyone has different answers.</p> <p><i>“Everyone has a different answer to each question. Over time, you may find that your responses vary for some items, but not others. There are no right or wrong answers. Be intuitive when answering. Don’t think too long and be honest. Your first response is usually the best response.”</i></p>																																	
<p>b) Explain that scores should reflect the past day on average.</p> <p><i>“Record how you feel on average throughout the day: from waking up till the time you complete the survey.”</i></p>																																	
<p>c) Explain the scale:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scale ranges from 1-7 - Use scale’s full range 	<p><i>“Each item is measured on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 usually meaning ‘not at all’, 4 meaning ‘moderately’, and 7 meaning ‘very much’. You can use the numbers in between to give more nuance or detail to your responses. For example, if you feel you have been stressed quite a lot but not ‘very much’, you could record a 6.</i></p> <p><i>“You’re welcome to score as low as ‘1’ or as high as ‘7’ if they feel appropriate to you. Please use the full range of the scale as this helps to reflect the full extent of your thoughts and feelings.”</i></p>																																
<p>d) Go through the questions together.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ask participants to verbalise their thoughts. - Ensure they understand each question. <p>Important: Guide participants to answer 4 (moderately) to each question during the orientation session. This will ensure that this survey entry will be excluded during the data cleaning phase.</p>	<p><i>“Let’s go through the questions together and make sure they make sense to you. For the purposes of this walkthrough, please respond 4 (moderately) to every question right now.”</i></p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>‘I felt cheerful’</td> <td>“How happy and joyful did you feel today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt stressed’</td> <td>“Did you feel stressful or tense today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt down’</td> <td>“Did you feel unhappy or low today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt strange’</td> <td>“Did you or the world around you seem weirder than other days, today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt content’</td> <td>“Did you feel satisfied with how things turned out today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt suspicious of others’</td> <td>“Did you find it hard to trust other people today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt relaxed’</td> <td>“Did you feel calm and peaceful today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘My thoughts were racing’</td> <td>“Were your thoughts going very fast, or too fast in your mind, today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt enthusiastic’</td> <td>“Did you feel excited about things today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I heard things that others could not hear’</td> <td>“Did you hear sounds or voices that others did not seem to notice today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt empty’</td> <td>“Did you feel hollow or vacant today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt anxious’</td> <td>“Did you feel nervous and uneasy today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I could concentrate well’</td> <td>“How well were you able to focus on things you needed or wanted to do today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt irritable’</td> <td>“Did you feel grumpy, short-tempered, or easily annoyed today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I felt worried’</td> <td>“Did you feel troubled or concerned today?”</td> </tr> <tr> <td>‘I could enjoy nice things when they happened’</td> <td>“How well were you able to experience positive feelings when nice events happened today?”</td> </tr> </table>	‘I felt cheerful’	“How happy and joyful did you feel today?”	‘I felt stressed’	“Did you feel stressful or tense today?”	‘I felt down’	“Did you feel unhappy or low today?”	‘I felt strange’	“Did you or the world around you seem weirder than other days, today?”	‘I felt content’	“Did you feel satisfied with how things turned out today?”	‘I felt suspicious of others’	“Did you find it hard to trust other people today?”	‘I felt relaxed’	“Did you feel calm and peaceful today?”	‘My thoughts were racing’	“Were your thoughts going very fast, or too fast in your mind, today?”	‘I felt enthusiastic’	“Did you feel excited about things today?”	‘I heard things that others could not hear’	“Did you hear sounds or voices that others did not seem to notice today?”	‘I felt empty’	“Did you feel hollow or vacant today?”	‘I felt anxious’	“Did you feel nervous and uneasy today?”	‘I could concentrate well’	“How well were you able to focus on things you needed or wanted to do today?”	‘I felt irritable’	“Did you feel grumpy, short-tempered, or easily annoyed today?”	‘I felt worried’	“Did you feel troubled or concerned today?”	‘I could enjoy nice things when they happened’	“How well were you able to experience positive feelings when nice events happened today?”
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	‘I felt that others could read my mind’	“Did you feel like other people could access your thoughts directly today?”
	‘I felt lonely’	“Did you feel alone today?”
	‘I felt very special’	“Did you feel like you were different from other people today?”
	‘I felt energetic’	“Did you feel like you had the energy to do things today?”
	‘I felt that others could control me’	“Did you feel like you were under other people’s control or direct influence?”
	‘I felt motivated’	“Did you feel like doing something or being active today?”
	‘I felt like my thoughts were confused or blocked’	“Did you feel like your had difficulty following your thoughts or that you had a hard time thinking clearly?”
	‘I saw things that others could not see’	“Did you see people or things (like shadows, animals, or lights) that others did not seem to notice today?”
	‘I could handle what came my way’	“How well were you able to cope or deal with things today?”
	‘I was able to function well’	“Did you feel like you could do what you needed or wanted to do today?”
	‘I spent time with other people (live)’	“How much time did you spend in the company of other people, face-to-face?”
	‘I spent time with other people (online/digitally)’	“How much time did you spend in the company of others, online (e.g., via FaceTime, WhatsApp or Zoom)?”
	‘I experienced a negative or unpleasant event’	“How many times did you experience something which you found negative, stressful, or unpleasant?”
	‘I experienced a positive or pleasant event’	“How many times did you experience something which you found positive, nice, or pleasant?”
	‘Feel free to go to the voice diary’	This final item is an invitation to tell us something about how you have been doing or feeling lately in the voice diary. Here you can simply talk about what’s on your mind.
<p>2. Voice Diaries</p> <p>Note: In actuality, mindLAMP allows for a maximum recording time of 4 minutes but we are guiding participants to limit it to 2 minutes to reduce the burden of the team transcribing the diaries.</p>	<p><i>“The last question is an invitation for you to complete a voice diary.</i></p> <p><i>The voice diaries are helpful because they allow you to record any relevant or meaningful experiences you might have that are not covered by the survey questions.</i></p> <p><i>With voice diaries, you can talk about anything you want for two minutes. You can complete the voice diaries every day. Try to complete a voice diary at least once a week. Remember to record your voice diary in a private place. Please avoid recording other people’s conversations to protect their privacy. You may also feel more comfortable recording a diary when you’re alone.”</i></p>	
a) Emphasize safety .	“Please make sure you are safe when responding (e.g., not driving).”	

3. Personalised Feedback

- a) Participant may view their own responses via the Portal tab.
- b) On the Portal tab:
 - Click the (plus) icon next to 'Activity' if Daily Survey is not already displayed.
 - Select 'Daily Survey' and 'Done'.

- c) Click anywhere on the blue graph to view specific responses.
 - The graph displayed will show total survey scores over time, which will make little sense to the participant.
 - Select the (tile) icon to see individual survey question responses.

- d) Participants can now see their responses to each survey question.
 - The numerical value will display their most recent responses, with the latest response on the left.
 - The graphs will display their responses over time in chronological order.

3.5. Financial reimbursement schedule

Financial reimbursement will be based on the completion percentage of daily text surveys and voice diaries.

***Important**

- Non-Australian and American sites, please convert to your local currency.

1. Explain the financial reimbursement schedule to them as per the table below. Note that they will receive more reimbursement if they complete more surveys and voice diaries.

	PRESCIENT	ProNET																																																																																																																																		
	Schedule: - initial 10 AUD reimbursement (Month 0) - every month since EMA baseline	Schedule: every month since EMA baseline																																																																																																																																		
	Every month since baseline: 0.40 AUD per completed survey / audio diary Number of days completed x 0.40 = <u> </u> AUD	Every month since baseline: 2 USD per completed survey Number of days completed x 2 = <u> </u> USD																																																																																																																																		
Example scenario	Participant A completed the EMA baseline on 10 Jan 2023. They completed 20 surveys during the first month of the study (i.e., by 10 Feb 2023). They will receive: - 10 AUD reimbursement at baseline (10 Jan 2023) - 8 AUD at the end of Month 1 (10 Feb 2023)	Participant B completed the EMA baseline on 10 Jan 2023. Participant B completed 20 surveys during the first month of the study (i.e., by 10 Feb 2023). They will receive: - 40 USD in reimbursements at the end of Month 1 (10 Feb 2023)																																																																																																																																		
Payment calculation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login to DPDash 2. Search for the participant's AMPSCZ ID 3. Set the Configuration to "Digital Biomarker: Mindlamp Forms and QC (Monthly)" 4. Check corresponding month's "Days with EMA (#)" <div style="text-align: center;"> <table border="1" style="margin: 10px auto; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr> <th>ME00000 - ME</th> <th>0</th> <th>1</th> <th>2</th> <th>3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Assessment Month</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>Days since onboarding</td><td>1</td><td>31</td><td>62</td><td>92</td></tr> <tr><td>Days in the month</td><td>0</td><td>30</td><td>31</td><td>30</td></tr> <tr><td>Raw survey files (#)</td><td></td><td>30</td><td>31</td><td>18</td></tr> <tr><td>Raw passive files (#)</td><td></td><td>30</td><td>31</td><td>30</td></tr> <tr><td>Avg size of survey files (Kb)</td><td></td><td>6</td><td>6</td><td>6</td></tr> <tr><td>Avg size of passive files (Mb)</td><td></td><td>67</td><td>92</td><td>90</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with EMA (#)</td><td></td><td>27</td><td>31</td><td>18</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with EMA (%)</td><td></td><td>90</td><td>100</td><td>60</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with Accelerometer (%)</td><td></td><td>83</td><td>100</td><td>100</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with Phone Use (%)</td><td></td><td>97</td><td>100</td><td>100</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with Phone GPS (%)</td><td></td><td>87</td><td>100</td><td>100</td></tr> </tbody> </table> </div> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Calculation: - "Days with EMA (#)" x 0.40 AUD = <u> </u> AUD (total reimbursement to be given) <p>Example: Participant C completed 27 surveys in Month 1. 27 x 0.40 AUD = 10.80 AUD</p>	ME00000 - ME	0	1	2	3	Assessment Month	0	1	2	3	Days since onboarding	1	31	62	92	Days in the month	0	30	31	30	Raw survey files (#)		30	31	18	Raw passive files (#)		30	31	30	Avg size of survey files (Kb)		6	6	6	Avg size of passive files (Mb)		67	92	90	Days with EMA (#)		27	31	18	Days with EMA (%)		90	100	60	Days with Accelerometer (%)		83	100	100	Days with Phone Use (%)		97	100	100	Days with Phone GPS (%)		87	100	100	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login to DPDash 2. Search for the participant's AMPSCZ ID 3. Set the Configuration to "Digital Biomarker: Mindlamp Forms and QC (Monthly)" 4. Check corresponding month's "Days with EMA (#)" <div style="text-align: center;"> <table border="1" style="margin: 10px auto; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr> <th>ME00000 - ME</th> <th>0</th> <th>1</th> <th>2</th> <th>3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Assessment Month</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>Days since onboarding</td><td>1</td><td>31</td><td>62</td><td>92</td></tr> <tr><td>Days in the month</td><td>0</td><td>30</td><td>31</td><td>30</td></tr> <tr><td>Raw survey files (#)</td><td></td><td>30</td><td>31</td><td>18</td></tr> <tr><td>Raw passive files (#)</td><td></td><td>30</td><td>31</td><td>30</td></tr> <tr><td>Avg size of survey files (Kb)</td><td></td><td>6</td><td>6</td><td>6</td></tr> <tr><td>Avg size of passive files (Mb)</td><td></td><td>67</td><td>92</td><td>90</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with EMA (#)</td><td></td><td>27</td><td>31</td><td>18</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with EMA (%)</td><td></td><td>90</td><td>100</td><td>60</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with Accelerometer (%)</td><td></td><td>83</td><td>100</td><td>100</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with Phone Use (%)</td><td></td><td>97</td><td>100</td><td>100</td></tr> <tr><td>Days with Phone GPS (%)</td><td></td><td>87</td><td>100</td><td>100</td></tr> </tbody> </table> </div> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Calculation: - "Days with EMA (#)" x 2 USD = <u> </u> USD (total reimbursement to be given) <p>Example: Participant D completed 27 surveys in Month 1. 27 x 2 USD = 54 USD</p>	ME00000 - ME	0	1	2	3	Assessment Month	0	1	2	3	Days since onboarding	1	31	62	92	Days in the month	0	30	31	30	Raw survey files (#)		30	31	18	Raw passive files (#)		30	31	30	Avg size of survey files (Kb)		6	6	6	Avg size of passive files (Mb)		67	92	90	Days with EMA (#)		27	31	18	Days with EMA (%)		90	100	60	Days with Accelerometer (%)		83	100	100	Days with Phone Use (%)		97	100	100	Days with Phone GPS (%)		87	100	100
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2. **PRESCIENT:** Reimburse participants with the 10 AUD initial reimbursement at orientation/baseline.

3.6. Discuss practicalities and wrap up

1. Provide participants with an email address or phone number so that they can contact you if they experience any issues or have any questions.	
2. Explain that they do not need to change their daily routines.	
3. Agree upon monthly check-in. Important: - Where possible, one RA should be assigned to the same participant for the duration of the study to build a more personal relationship . - Monthly check-ins can be combined with onsite assessment.	<i>“Every month, I will be in touch to discuss how you’re going with the daily surveys and discuss any issues you need help with.”</i> <i>I will be checking your progress. Although I will be able to see how many surveys you have completed, your data will be confidential and deidentified.</i>
4. AMP_SCZ v1: Full Study and AMP_SCZ v2: Full Study Without GPS: Remind participant to <u>keep phone charged</u> and <u>never enable low power / battery saving mode</u> . This is to ensure that the passive sensors can function properly.	
5. Suggest setting a calendar reminder at 8:30pm.	
6. End with motivating the participant.	<i>“Other participants have said that they got used to answering daily surveys and even looked forward to reflecting on their day. Most of our participants found the surveys manageable. You will be contributing to state-of-the-art research. We really appreciate your participation.”</i>
7. Answer any remaining questions.	<i>“I’m giving you a lot of information right now but once you start, you’ll find it very easy. Do you have any questions?”</i>

4. Monitoring progress – monthly check-in (DPDash)

- DPDash is designed to manage and visualise multiple data streams over an extended period of time.
- If there are any issues with DPDash (e.g., unable to view participant data), please contact either Habib Rahimi Eichl (hrahimieichi@mgb.org) or Yoonho Chung (ychung3@mgb.org) from DPACC/PREDICT.

4.1. Digital Phenotyping Dashboard (DPDash) overview

1. Login to [DPDash](#).

Notes:

- Copy this if the link above does not work: <https://predict.bwh.harvard.edu/dpdash/>
- DPDash is best viewed on Google Chrome.
- If you do not have access to DPDash, please contact your Site Investigator so they can add you to the NDA Data User Certification (DUC).

2. Overview of DPDash

PARTICIPANT	STUDY	LAST SYNCED	COMPLETE	STAR
ME00000	ME	Today	<input type="checkbox"/>	★
ME00001	ME	Today	<input type="checkbox"/>	★
ME00002	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆
ME00003	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆
ME00004	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆
ME00005	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆
ME00006	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆

3. Search for a study participant by typing in their AMPSCZ ID in the search bar.

4. Select the participant's AMPSCZ ID.

5. Select the Configuration (config.) of interest from the drop-down list:

- combined-digital_biomarker (Yearly)
- Digital Biomarker: Mindlamp Forms and QC (Monthly)
- Digital Biomarker: Axivity+Mindlamp (Daily)

a) **Yearly:**
combined-digital_biomarker

- Data relevant for filing up EMA RPMS (PRESCIENT) / REDCap (ProNET) form are outlined in red

Participant	ME00000
Days in Study	407
Days since Mindlamp Onboarding	350
Mindlamp Version (1, 2, or 3)	1
Phone Accelerometer: All Available (>6h) Days (#)	328
Percentage Availability (%)	94
Data Quality (Avg hours per day) (hr)	19
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	4
Data Quality (1= <6h/day to 4= >18h/day)	4
Phone Screen: All Available (>=1h) Days (#)	336
Percentage Availability (%)	96
Data Quality (Avg hours per day) (hr)	14
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	4
Data Quality (1= <6h/day to 4= >18h/day)	3
Phone GPS: All Available (>6h) Days (#)	317
Percentage Availability (%)	91
Data Quality (Avg hours per day) (hr)	18
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	4
Data Quality (1= <6h/day to 4= >18h/day)	3
Phone EMA: All Available (complete) Days (#)	217
Percentage Availability (%)	62
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	3
Days since Axivity Onboarding	349
Activity: All Available (>=20h) Days (#)	273
Percentage Availability (%)	85
Data Quality (Avg hours per day) (hr)	23
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	4
Data Quality (1= <6h/day to 4= >18h/day)	4

b) **Monthly:**
Digital Biomarker: Mindlamp Forms and QC

- Main config. to use when conducting follow-up:
 - o Red box: Cells coloured orange and below = < 15 days / 50% threshold
 - o Blue box: Month 0 column expected to be blank (no data at baseline)

	EMA baseline (orientation)	1 st follow up – exactly 1 month from baseline (e.g., 5 May – 5 June)					Final follow up – on Day 365		
Assessment Month	0	1	2	3	4	10	11	12	
Days since onboarding	1	32	62	93	123	305	335	351	
Days in the month	0	31	30	31	30	31	30	16	
Raw survey files (#)		23	17	16	13	23	18	6	
Raw passive files (#)		30	30	31	30	30	30	16	
Avg size of passive files (KB)		6	6	6	6	7	6	6	
Avg size of passive files (MB)		58	53	64	55	61	63	87	
Days with EMA (#)		22	16	16	12	25	18	5	
Days with EMA (%)		71	53	52	40	81	60	31	
Days with Accelerometer (%)		94	93	97	77	87	93	100	
Days with Phone Use (%)		94	93	100	77	94	100	100	
Days with Phone GPS (%)		94	93	97	77	77	87	81	
Accelerometer Quality (%)		61	61	70	62	67	68	90	
Use Quality (%)		45	36	48	44	50	53	65	
GPS Quality (%)		67	63	71	80	55	63	88	
Message Exist?									

c) **Daily:**
Digital Biomarker: Axivity+Mindlamp

- Daily view not essential for follow-up but helpful for investigating specific issues (e.g., poor GPS quality observed from Monthly view)

6. Utilising address bar

- Quickly switch between participants by editing the address bar
- Only include site ID to view all participants from one site

<https://predict.bwh.harvard.edu/dpdash/dashboard/ME/ME00000>

<https://predict.bwh.harvard.edu/dpdash/dashboard/ME/>

4.2. One-week check-in after orientation/baseline

<p>1. Complete a quick check-in with participant <u>one week after</u> digital orientation/baseline. This can be completed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) During appointments for other assessments (e.g., EEG, MRI, blood biomarkers, speech) b) Over a phone call c) Over a text message 	<p><i>“Hi NAME, just wanted to touch base with you. How are you doing? Are the surveys coming in fine? Is the app working okay?”</i></p>
<p>2. Note that check-in was completed (with important notes, if any), in the “Record any protocol deviations and notes” field in the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) EMA – Month 1 on RPMS (PRESCIENT) b) Digital Biomarkers Mindlamp Checkin – Month 1 on REDCap (ProNET) 	<p>Example:</p> <p><i>“One-week check-in completed. Participant not receiving survey notification, have advised them to set a calendar reminder on their phone. Issue logged in mindLAMP Bug Report Form (11 Aug 2023).”</i></p>

4.3. Pre-monthly check in – data quality check

- Check data quality before monthly check-ins to discuss the participant’s progress with them

<p>1. Survey data quality:</p> <p>a) On DPDash, select the Digital Biomarker: Mindlamp Forms and QC (Monthly) config.</p>	
<p>b) If cells for ...</p> <p>“Days with EMA (#)” “Days with EMA (%)”</p> <p>... are coloured light yellow and above (more than 50% completion), go through Section 4.4.4a with participant</p> <p>... are coloured light orange and below (less than 50% completion), go through Section 4.4.4b to 4.4.6 with participant</p>	
<p>2. Passive data quality</p> <p>a) Open the mindLAMP Poor Passive Data QC Report:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PRESCIENT (link) - ProNET (link) <p>b) If the participant is listed in the Report, go through Section 4.5 with them</p>	<p>Copy the URL below if the link to the left does not work:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PRESCIENT https://app.box.com/s/v99ku7rvdt0iu4vxegr6eq9690knpia

4.4. Monthly check-in – surveys (EMA)

<p>1. Note the participant’s monthly percentage of completion on RPMS (PRESCIENT) / REDCap (ProNET) from the Digital Biomarker: Mindlamp Forms and QC (Monthly) config. (DPDash)</p>	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="border: none;">Assessment Month</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">0</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">1</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">2</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">3</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">4</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">Days since onboarding</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">1</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">32</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">62</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">93</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">123</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">Days in the month</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">0</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">31</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">30</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">31</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">30</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">...</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">Days with EMA (#)</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;"></td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">22</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">16</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">16</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">12</td> </tr> <tr style="border: 2px solid red;"> <td style="border: none;">Days with EMA (%)</td> <td style="border: none;"></td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">71</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">53</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">52</td> <td style="background-color: #e6f2ff;">40</td> </tr> </table> <p>The date range for the monthly percentage is exactly a month from the previous check-in (e.g., 3 Apr – 3 May), starting from the Month 0 assessment date (baseline).</p> <p>Example</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 60%;">Month 0 Assessment Date</td> <td>15 January 2022</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Month 1 Assessment Date</td> <td>15 February 2022</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Month 1’s Monthly Percentage</td> <td>15 January – 14 February 2022</td> </tr> </table>	Assessment Month	0	1	2	3	4	Days since onboarding	1	32	62	93	123	Days in the month	0	31	30	31	30	...						Days with EMA (#)		22	16	16	12	Days with EMA (%)		71	53	52	40	Month 0 Assessment Date	15 January 2022	Month 1 Assessment Date	15 February 2022	Month 1’s Monthly Percentage	15 January – 14 February 2022
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Month 1’s Monthly Percentage	15 January – 14 February 2022																																										
<p>2. Discuss participant’s progress.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can be conducted over a phone call, video call or during onsite visit (e.g., during EEG). 	<p><i>“How have the surveys been going for you over the past month?”</i></p>																																										
<p>3. Check that permission settings are still enabled.</p>	<p><i>“Are all the necessary permissions still enabled on your phone? (e.g., notifications, audio)”</i></p>																																										
<p>4. Discuss observed survey data quality.</p>	<p>a) If they completed most surveys (<50% missing): <i>“Just letting you know that you have completed ___% of surveys this month. That’s amazing. Keep it up!”</i></p> <p>b) If they missed many surveys (>50% missing): <i>“I see that you have missed quite a few surveys. Do you know why this may be the case? Is there anything I can do to help?”</i></p>																																										
<p>5. Identify the reason for missing surveys and look for solutions together.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical problems: Identify technical issues with participant. See Section 4.5. - Practical problems: See how you can help (e.g., set extra reminders, give letters to explain their participation to employers, etc.) - Motivational problems: Discuss why they feel unmotivated. Express your understanding, especially in case of shame of participant. Emphasize the importance of compliance in these EMA studies. 	<p><i>“Do you think it’s due to technical/ practical/ motivational problems? How can we help to fix them?”</i></p> <p><i>“I understand it can be difficult to keep it up. It does take a lot of effort to do this every day. But I can assure you that it gets easier the more you do them. It will be as routine as taking a shower or brushing your teeth!”</i></p> <p><i>“I understand that doing these surveys every day can be really challenging, especially if you’re not feeling great. That’s OK. Let’s try for a couple more weeks.”</i></p> <p><i>“I’d like to remind you that you’re doing very important work here. Your data helps us learn more about mental health! Although it’s challenging, I’d like to ask you to try and keep up the good work!”</i></p>																																										
<p>6. Remind them about reimbursement and personalised feedback.</p>	<p><i>“The more surveys you complete, the more money you can earn and the more insight you will get from your own data.”</i></p>																																										

4.5. Monthly check-in – passive sensor data

- If the participant is listed in the Poor Passive Data QC Report ([PRESCIENT/ProNET](#)), go through the checklist below for troubleshooting.

<p>Ask the participants, “<i>We noticed that your phone is not sending a lot of passive sensor data (such as GPS and accelerometer). Before going further, do you have any idea why that might be?</i>”</p>	
a) Is the participant currently logged in?	Ask them to open the app to check if they are logged in. If they have deleted it by accident, guide them to reinstall it (Section 3.2).
b) Are the required permissions granted correctly in Settings?	<p>Study Version 1 Set location access to “Always Allow” for mindLAMP app.</p> <p>Study Version 2 If accelerometer and device state sensor data quality is poor, guide the participants to enable location permissions. For some phone models, location access operates as a ‘gateway’ for collecting other sensors and enabling it may improve data flow. Even if location access is enabled, <u>location data will not be collected</u> if participants are enrolled in Study Version 2.</p>
c) Is the phone operating on low power or battery saver mode?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Low power & battery saver mode prevents the app from collecting sensor data. Ask them to open Settings. Ensure that low power or battery saver mode is disabled. ii. If their phone has battery optimisation features, guide them to deactivate it. iii. If passive data quality remains poor, guide them to uninstall and reinstall the app.
d) Has the participant encountered a bug in the app (e.g., white screen, app not loading, etc.)?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Guide them to reinstall and login into the app. ii. If the issue persists, fill in the mindLAMP Bug Report Form.
e) Is the phone’s device storage / memory full?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. If the device's storage is close to full, this may interfere with passive data collection. Ask if freeing up storage on their device is possible. ii. (Android users) Clear data. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Go to Settings > mindLAMP > Storage & Cache > Clear cache - This can help clear stored data on the device, allowing mindLAMP to run more effectively.
f) Is airplane mode turned off?	Ask them to verify this from their home screen or Settings. If airplane mode was turned on and then off at some point, this will not compromise data quality.
g) Is the device consistently connected to Wi-Fi?	Data can be locally stored in mindLAMP but won’t be uploaded to the server without Wi-Fi. Ask the participant to let you know the next time they connect to Wi-Fi and check to see if data is uploaded to the server.
h) Is the device powered on most of the times of the day?	Data cannot be collected when the phone is off.
i) Is the participant experiencing technical issues not documented or resolvable by the previous troubleshooting steps?	Fill in the mindLAMP Bug Report Form here: https://forms.gle/UzXed2jZuPG1HnbA

PRESCIENT

- j) If troubleshooting was performed, document the process in the “RA comments” field on RPMS in the corresponding monthly check-in form

EMA at Time Point: Month 7

RA comments:

Please click if this form is missing all of its data

ProNET

- j) If troubleshooting was performed, document the process in the “chrdig_notes_6” field on REDCap in the corresponding monthly check-in form

Are all the necessary permissions still enabled on your phone? (e.g., notifications, gps, audio)

1. Are you currently signed into your mindlamp account?
2. (for Study Ver. 1 & 2) Make sure your phone is not on low power / battery saver mode?
3. (for Study Ver. 1 & 2) Did you give permission for the mindlamp app to access gps, and set it to 'always allow'?

2. Checked that permission settings are still enabled.

Notes ← Document passive sensor data QC or phone permission troubleshooting related notes in this section ("chrdig_notes_6")

Expand

- k) See below for example texts:

- “Participant was listed in poor passive QC Report”
- “Passive sensing troubleshooting performed”
- “All phone config was set correctly. Encouraged participants to continue filling out surveys”
- “Phone was in low battery mode, reminded to avoid low battery mode whenever possible etc.”
- “GPS permission was set to not allowed. Now set to ‘Always allow’ ”.
- “mindLAMP app does not load (only see white screen)”

5. Ad hoc correspondence and procedures

5.1 Enrolled participants changing study versions

- If a participant wants to swap study versions, this **must be recorded** appropriately on RPMS (PRESCIENT) and REDCap (ProNET) to comply with DPACC and NIMH's guidance (e.g., reimbursement, consent purposes, data cohesion, etc.).

1. If not already completed, re-consent the participant with the new study version									
2. Rename the participant's old LAMP ID alias with "old" written in parentheses Important Do not delete their old mindLAMP account	<input type="checkbox"/> ME00000 (old)								
3. Create a new LAMP ID with the new study version. - Complete Section 2.1 , 2.2 and 2.3.1 Important Do not override or modify the orientation / onboarding form (Month 0).									
4. Note the changes on RPMS / REDCap in the corresponding month where this change occurred	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>B. Has the participant's details changed?</td> <td>1. Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B1. Date of change(s):</td> <td>12/08/2023</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B2. New Study Version?</td> <td>3. Yes - AMP_SC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B3. New LAMP ID?</td> <td>1. Yes U0123456789</td> </tr> </table>	B. Has the participant's details changed?	1. Yes	B1. Date of change(s):	12/08/2023	B2. New Study Version?	3. Yes - AMP_SC	B3. New LAMP ID?	1. Yes U0123456789
B. Has the participant's details changed?	1. Yes								
B1. Date of change(s):	12/08/2023								
B2. New Study Version?	3. Yes - AMP_SC								
B3. New LAMP ID?	1. Yes U0123456789								
5. Email your network's digital study coordinator and the DPACC representative about the change with the following details: a) AMPSCZ ID b) Old LAMP ID c) New LAMP ID d) Date of change	<p>PRESCIENT Sophie Tod – sophie.tod@orygen.org.au</p> <p>ProNET Angela Nuñez – angela.nunez@yale.edu</p> <p>DPACC Yoonho Chung – y chung3@mgb.org</p>								

5.2 Non-participant-triggered missing surveys

1. Participants must be reimbursed for days they are unable to complete surveys due to technical issues. This includes (but is not limited to): a) mindLAMP server downtime (e.g., server maintenance) b) mindLAMP app malfunction (e.g., app crashing, white screen, etc.)	
2. Note the number of missing surveys on RPMS / REDCap in the corresponding month's form	C. Number of missing surveys due to technical issues (not participant triggered): <input type="text"/>
3. When calculating reimbursement, add the number of missing surveys to the total	<p>Example</p> <p>Participant C from Melbourne completed 27 surveys in Month 1. There were 3 days of missing surveys due to technical issues. (27 + 3) x 0.40 AUD = 12 AUD</p>

6. End of study participation

1. Premature ending of study participation (withdrawing)

Note premature end on RPMS (PRESCIENT) / REDCap (ProNET):

A. Is the participant still part of the study?	0. No	↓
A1. Total percentage of surveys completed:	78.0	%
A2. Reimbursement total (specify currency):	72.0	1. AUD ↓
A3. Thanked the participant for all their efforts and contribution:	1. Yes	↓
A4. Ensured they received their reimbursement. Keep records of payment according to local requirements:	1. Yes	↓
A5. Terminated their participation by asking them to delete the app:	1. Yes	↓

If they are opting out from only EMA

1. In the upcoming check-in form and all subsequent forms:

a. Note the **reason** and **date** of withdrawal in the 'RA comments' field:

RA comments:

b. Tick 'Please click if this form is missing all of its data'

Please click if this form is missing all of its data

c. Select 'M1 – Measure refusal'

Please specify the reason for missing data on this form M1 – Measure refusal

If they are opting out of all digital components (both EMA & actigraphy)

1. In the upcoming check-in form and all subsequent forms:

a. Note the **reason** and **date** of withdrawal in the 'RA comments' field:

RA comments:

b. Tick 'Please click if this form is missing all of its data'

Please click if this form is missing all of its data

c. Select 'M1 – Measure refusal'

Please specify the reason for missing data on this form M1 – Measure refusal

2. (PRESCIENT) Complete the MissingData form as per Section 13.2 of the [Data Upload SOP](#) (Section 13.2)

Important

Do not delete the participant's mindLAMP account from the dashboard.

2. Both premature and regular ending of study participation at the end of the 12-month study period

- Thank the participant for all their efforts and contribution.
- Ensure they receive their reimbursement. Keep record of reimbursement as per local requirement.
- Terminate their participation by asking them to delete the app.

Appendix

A.1. EMA items and related constructs	STEM FORMULATION	Response scale
	“Today I felt _____”	1-7
	STEM SPECIFIER	CONSTRUCT
	Energetic	Positive Valence / Arousal
	Cheerful	Positive Valence / Arousal
	Content	Positive Valence / Arousal
	Relaxed	Positive Valence / Arousal
	Enthusiastic	Positive Valence / Arousal
	Down	Negative Valence / Arousal
	Empty	Flat affect
	Anxious	Negative Valence / Arousal
	Stressed	Negative Valence / Arousal
	Irritable	Negative Valence / Arousal
	Worried	Negative Valence / Arousal
	Lonely	Negative Valence / Arousal
	Suspicious of others	Positive Symptoms
	Very special	Positive Symptoms
	Strange	Positive Symptoms
	That others could read my mind	Positive Symptoms
	That others could control me	Positive Symptoms
	Like my thoughts felt confused or blocked	Disorganized thoughts
	STEM FORMULATION	Response scale
	“Today _____”	1-7
	STEM SPECIFIER	CONSTRUCT
	I saw things that others couldn't see	Positive Symptoms
	I heard things that others couldn't hear	Positive Symptoms
	I could concentrate well	Resilience
	I could handle what came my way	Resilience
I could enjoy nice things when they happened	Anhedonia	
I spent time with other people (live)	Social behaviour	
I spent time with other people (online/digitally)	Social behaviour	
I felt motivated	Resilience	
I was able to function well	Functional	
I experienced a negative/unpleasant event	Events	
I experienced a positive/pleasant event	Events	
Feel free to go to the voice diary*		
A.2. Troubleshooting	<p><u>Report bugs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To report bugs or issues, report your issue using the mindLAMP Bug Report Form: https://forms.gle/UzXed2jZuPG1HnbA. <p><u>Login issues</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If you experience login issues (e.g., getting logged out of app), please contact team@digitalpsych.org. 	
A.3. mindLAMP dashboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do not delete any participant accounts, both existing and those who have withdrawn. - Do not delete or change any Sensors or Activities. If there are any issues with the setup, please contact the personnels in the title page of this SOP. 	
A.4. Useful links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mindLAMP user guide (link) - Frequently asked questions (link) 	
A.5. DPDash guide	<p>Detailed information about DPDash for digital data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slides (link) - Video (link) 	